

Coordination Chemistry of Quinquevalent Molybdenum— 2,2' Bipyridyl and 1,10 Phenanthroline Complexes

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In our previous communication¹ we reported the preparation and properties of 2, 2' bipyridyl and 1, 10 phenanthroline salts of oxypentachloromolybdic (V) acid². Recently, while investigating the properties of these salts we have been able to isolate a few interesting color isomers of the general formula $\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot \text{bipy}$ and $\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot \text{phen}$ (where bipy is 2,2 bipyridyl and phen is 1, 10 phenanthroline). Mitchell³ and Spengler and Gansheimer⁴ have reported, of course, only one such variety in these cases, although their starting material and method of preparation were entirely different. Methods of analysis and determination of oxidation state used are the same as described in our previous publication¹. Magnetic measurements were made with Guoy balance of field strength 8500 gauss and the values recorded here are as $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.839 (X'_M T)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ where X'_M = molar susceptibility after diamagnetic correction and T is absolute temperature.

Method of Preparation:

(a) $\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot \text{bipy}$ (red) and $\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot \text{phen}$ (pink) were isolated by refluxing the corresponding salts of oxypentachloromolybdic (V) acid in absolute alcohol. The products were dried to constant weight in a vacuum desiccator.

(b) $\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot \text{bipy}$ (green) and $\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot \text{phen}$ (green) were isolated by refluxing the corresponding salts of oxypentachloromolybdic (V) acid in acetonitrile. The products were dried to constant weight in vacuum desiccator.

(c) $\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot \text{bipy}$ (pale khaki) and $\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot \text{phen}$ (pale brown) were isolated by prolonged boiling $\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot \text{bipy}$ (red) and $\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot \text{phen}$ (pink) compounds in hydrochloric acid. The compounds were dried over solid KOH in vacuum desiccator.

Results of analysis are given in Table I.

TABLE I

Compounds	Color	Found			Calculated			μ_{eff} B.M.
		Mo (%)	Cl (%)	N (%)	Mo (%)	Cl (%)	N (%)	
$\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot \text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2$	Red	25.68	27.45	7.44	25.64	28.41	7.48	1.60
	Bright green	25.52	28.45	7.40	"	"	"	1.76
	Pale khaki	25.34	27.85	7.43	"	"	"	1.73
$\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot \text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2$	Pink	24.01	25.95	6.94	24.09	26.70	7.03	1.54
	Olive green	24.04	26.54	6.95	"	"	"	1.76
	Pale brown	24.39	26.02	6.68	"	"	"	1.75

1. M. C. Halder and H. K. Saha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 231.

2. H. K. Saha and M. C. Halder, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 741.

3. P. C. H. Mitchell, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1963, **25**, 963.

4. G. Spengler and J. Gansheimer, *Angew. Chem.*, 1957, **69**, 523.

It appears from the nature of products that the nonelectrolytic compounds are formed from the salts by the removal of hydrogen chloride as follows:

All these compounds are hardly affected by water and only slightly soluble in nitrobenzene and acetone etc. Oxidation state determination by ceric sulphate method indicates the presence of quinquevalent molybdenum in these compounds which also is in excellent agreement with the "spin only" values of magnetic moment corresponding to one unpaired electron. There is every possibility that compounds of the type $\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot \text{bipy}$ (or phen) may exist in cis-trans forms. However detail investigations including spectroscopic and X-ray methods etc. are in progress which will be reported later on.

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